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A novel hyper twist power take-off for coastal structure integrated wave energy converters

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Abstract

Coastal structure integrated wave energy converters (CSI WECs) represent an opportunity to harness wave energy resources, while taking advantage of onshore and near shore infrastructure. This existing infrastructure can provide a convenient platform to assist with installation, operations and maintenance (IO&M), lowering the costs of deployment and operation. Current deployments of CSI WECs use a hydraulic power take off (PTO) to capture the energy from the low frequency periodic motion of the waves, then use that high-pressure fluid to drive a turbine coupled to a generator to produce electricity.

This research investigates replacing that hydraulic PTO with a novel PTO based on a mechanical hypertwist phenomenon. The hypertwist phenomenon occurs when a rotor is supported on a loop of cord, such that rotation of the rotor causes the lines of the loop to wind or 'twist'. In the twisted state an axial load on the ends of the loop will cause the rotor to accelerate and spin in one direction. Inertia in the rotor will cause it to spin past the neutral, untwisted state and begin to wind in the other direction. Applying another axial load will cause the rotor to accelerate again, this time in the other direction. In this way, periodic linear motion is transformed into high speed rotational motion. Intuitively this seems like a promising phenomenon for transforming the high force, low velocity motion of waves into the high-speed rotational motion needed for efficient electricity generation.

Though largely untapped for industrial applications, this hypertwist phenomenon has been observed for centuries in children's toys called buzzers or whirligigs. More recently, researchers have explored applying this phenomenon to human powered centrifuges in the developing world. These low-cost devices were able to achieve rotational speeds of 100,000 RPM, powered only by a human operator pulling on a loop of string.

This research employed a combination of physics-based modeling in MATLAB Simscape and physical prototyping to explore the feasibility of using the hypertwist phenomenon to drive a permanent magnet generator, which could be integrated into a CSI WEC. Analytical equations for hypertwist dynamics were integrated into the Simscape model of mechanical motion, which was then coupled with a standard Simscape permanent magnet generator block. The electrical output from the generator was connected to a simple rectifier circuit where the average and peak powers were recorded. The resulting model was simulated across a variety of regular and irregular forcing functions, representing anticipated sea states. If successfully implemented in a CSI WEC, the hypertwist generator could offer benefits over the hydraulic PTO in the form of reduced losses from energy conversions and eliminating the risk of a potential hydraulic fluid leak in close proximity to the water.

Keywords: Wave Energy Converters, Power Take-Off, Coastal Structure Integrated WECs

1. Introduction and Motivation

Marine energy generation (both current energy converters and wave energy converters) is typically characterized by low velocities and high forces which are transformed via a power take off (PTO) to the higher rotational speeds required for electricity generation. This research aims to replace that mechanical gearbox or hydraulic PTO with a novel means of transforming slow, linear motion into high speed rotational motion via a hyper twist phenomenon found in a millennia old toy called a whirligig or buzzer. This hyper twist phenomenon has been successfully employed in human powered centrifuges for medical diagnostics in the developing world and could potentially be applied to wave energy generation.

A buzzer, spinner, or a whirligig is a child's toy or ceremonial artifact that consists of a looped string passing through two holes on a central plate. The resulting loop is then twisted and as loop is cyclically pulled in the axial direction it causes the plate to rotate as the loop unwinds. Inertia causes the plate to continue rotating past the unwound condition, rewinding the loop in the opposite direction and contracting the overall loop. Once wound in the other direction, the process repeats with a pull on the loop resulting in a rotation in the opposite direction. The basic embodiment of a traditional buzzer is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. A traditional whirligig toy from Ukraine [1]

While there had been some efforts to describe the physics of this toy [2], the first published engineering application of a buzzer whirligig appears in 2017 [3] when Stanford researchers developed a human powered centrifuge based around the whirligig design. The Stanford team tested a number of different sizes for the rotating disc and was able to produce rotational speeds of up to 125,000 RPM using an input frequency (pulsing of the loop) of under 2 Hz for the smallest spinning disc tested. More recently, researchers have developed a whirligig inspired triboelectric nanogenerator (Wi-TENG) as a lightweight human powered generator capable of charging a personal medical device like a glucose meter [4]. The Wi-TENG prototype uses the triboelectric effect to charge electrodes via the high-speed rotation (up to 11,250 RPM) of copper electrodes past a PTFE intermediary rotor.

The envisioned integration of the hyper twist PTO into a WEC starts by adding permanent magnets to the rotor and housing the rotor inside a stator to create a generator. The linear motion to provide the driving tension for the hyper twist rotor can be found wherever linear motion takes place in the existing WEC. WECs that include pivoting arms and pistons like the Eco Wave Power and Wavestar designs are seen as promising candidates as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. WEC topologies that include pistons as a potential candidate for hyper twist PTOs [5][6].

Modeling and Discussion

The ability to transform a low frequency drive (on the order of Hz) to a high frequency rotation (125,000 RPM) is attractive when looking at waves, with dominant frequencies of roughly 0.1 Hz. A similar transformation would have a rotor operating at suitable speeds for electricity generation. To explore the behavior of the whirligig physics when driven by wave like input, a Simscape model was created as shown in Figure 2 below. While the dynamics of an actual WEC are not considered at this stage the input force can be modeled as a square wave, regular sine wave, or an irregular wave built from a Bretschneider spectra. Physical constrains like the hard limits of rotation and string stiffness are modeled as well as the parameters for a rudimentary permanent magnet generator. Verification of the simulation results is achieved by comparison with experimental results from a hypertwist rotor test rig that reduces the variability from human powered operation.

Figure 3. Simscape model of a hypertwist generator with equations of motion from [3]

The Simscape model calculates the rotor position, angular velocity, and torque for a given input force profile as shown in Figure 4 below. Sharp changes in velocity are present in the simulation results that are not observed when

testing the physical prototypes. Those irregularities are currently being investigated, but are likely due to a) solver issues or b) the assumptions in modeling the limits of twist.

Beyond these suspect features, the data still suggests that the rotational speed can vary widely and abruptly, even for a simple sinusoidal force input. Given these wide swings in the rotational speed it would be difficult to keep a generator operating at an efficient setpoint. Future work and simulations will include mechanical and electrical concepts for smoothing out these velocities or the resulting electrical output.

3. Acknowledgments

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